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FAMOUS PIANISTS OF THE 21st CENTURY AND THEIR INTERPRETATIONS

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ЗНАМЕНИТЫЕ ПИАНИСТЫ XXI ВЕКА И ИХ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИИ

Abstract.

The evolutionary process and the principles of gradual development in 21st century piano music are closely related. The main goal of the article we present is the examination of the famous world piano players of the 21st century and their interpretations. The Russian piano school, which occupies an important place in world pianism, has produced a number of outstanding pianists. Among them, the names of Denis Matsuyev, Yevgeny Kissin, Nikolay Lugansky should be mentioned.

Denis Matsuyev is one of the pianists who became famous all over the world with his unique interpretations in modern times. He regularly cooperated with local orchestras and leading collectives of foreign countries and achieved high creative achievements. On April 8, 2019, Denis Matsuyev performed a grand concert program at the Heydar Aliyev Palace in Azerbaijan. First Lady Mehriban Aliyeva, her daughters Leyla Aliyeva and Arzu Aliyeva, who participated in the concert program, welcomed the pianist's interpretation with applause.

Yevgeny Igorevich Kissin is one of the famous representatives of the Russian piano school. The pianist is awarded two Grammy Awards in one competition: the first for the best solo performance of works by composers Scriabin and Stravinsky; and the second was received for the performance of Prokofiev's concerto for piano and orchestra.

Famous Russian pianist Nikolai Lugansky always wins the hearts of listeners with his interpretations. The pianist collaborates with the world's leading orchestras and more than 170 famous conductors.

*Although a generation of pianists such as Chen Sa, Li Yun-di, Shen Wenyu, Wang Yuichzia, and Zhang Haochen have been active in China in the 21st century, their performance art could not surpass the phenomenal achievements of Lang Lang. A distinctive feature of Lang Lang's playing style was his facial expressions and free movements behind the instrument. Until the 21st century, such free movements behind the instrument have not been seen in the interpretations of any professional pianist. Along with China, the role of South Korean musicians in the development of the world school of pianism is undeniable. Pianist Son-Jin Cho was the first Korean pianist to win the 1st prize and gold medal at the 2015 Chopin International Piano Competition in Warsaw. Contemporary Canadian pianist Ian Lisetsky's performances have been widely broadcast by leading radio and television networks in Europe and North America, and he was featured in the CBC National News documentary *The Prodigy*. Canadian pianist and composer Steve Barakatt has performed as a pianist for over 500 events regionally, nationally and internationally on many stages around the world. He continues to work as a producer and composer with musicians from Canada, South America and Asia.*

The prominent Turkish pianist of the 21st century, Fazil Say, continues composing and playing piano in parallel. Fazil Say performed at the grand Federal Presidential Concert in Germany in 2019, performing the works of well-known composers and several pieces he composed for this concert. The concert, attended by the President of Germany Frank-Walter Steinmeier and his wife, reverberates around the world.

With a combination of passionate musical feeling, high virtuosity and intellectual range, Icelandic pianist Víkingur Ólafsson has won all the honors in his country: four Musician of the Year awards at the Icelandic Music Awards, as well as the Icelandic Optimism Award. Humay Gasimzadeh, an Azerbaijani pianist who lives and works in America, is a graduate of the New York Manhattan School of Music. The pianist confirmed that he is a talented pianist by performing in the series of concert programs called "Musical Bridge" organized by the Azerbaijan-American Music Foundation. Among the pianists who lived and worked in Azerbaijan in the 21st century, we should especially emphasize the name of Murad Huseynov. His services in the development of the piano school in our country are undeniable.

Аннотация.

Эволюционный процесс и принципы постепенного развития фортепианной музыки XXI века тесно связаны. Основная цель представляемой нами статьи – рассмотрение известных мировых пианистов XXI века и их интерпретаций. Русская фортепианная школа, занимающая важное место в мировом пианизме, дала ряд выдающихся пианистов. Среди них следует назвать имена Дениса Мацуева, Евгения Кисина, Николая Луганского. Денис Мацуев – один из пианистов, прославившихся во всем мире своими уникальными интерпретациями в современности.

Он регулярно сотрудничал с местными оркестрами и ведущими коллективами зарубежных стран и добился высоких творческих достижений. 8 апреля 2019 года Денис Мацуев выступил с грандиозной концертной программой во Дворце Гейдара Алиева в Азербайджане. Первая леди Мехрибан Алиева, ее дочери Лейла Алиева и Арзу Алиева, участвовавшие в концертной программе, приветствовали исполнение пианиста аплодисментами.

Евгений Игоревич Кисин – один из известных представителей русской фортепианной школы. Пианист удостоен двух премий «Грэмми» в одном конкурсе: первую за лучшее сольное исполнение произведений композиторов Скрябина и Стравинского; а второй был получен за исполнение концерта Прокофьева для фортепиано с оркестром.

Известный российский пианист Николай Луганский всегда покоряет сердца слушателей своими интерпретациями. Пианист сотрудничает с ведущими оркестрами мира и более чем 170 известными дирижерами.

Хотя в XXI веке в Китае активно работало поколение пианистов, таких как Чэнь Са, Ли Юн-ди, Шэнь Вэнью, Ван Юйцзя и Чжан Хаочэнь, их исполнительское искусство не могло превзойти феноменальные достижения Лан Ланга. Отличительной чертой стиля игры Лан Ланга была мимика и свободные движения за инструментом. До XXI века столь свободные движения за инструментом не встречались в интерпретациях ни одного профессионального пианиста.

Наряду с Китаем неоспорима роль южнокорейских музыкантов в развитии мировой школы пианизма. Пианист Сон-Джин Чо был первым корейским пианистом, получившим первую премию и золотую медаль на Международном конкурсе пианистов имени Шопена в Варшаве в 2015 году.

Выступления современного канадского пианиста Яна Лисецкого широко транслировались ведущими радио- и телекомпаниями Европы и Северной Америки, а также он был показан в документальном фильме CBC National News «The Prodigy». Канадский пианист и композитор Стив Баракатт выступал в качестве пианиста на более чем 500 мероприятиях регионального, национального и международного уровня на многих сценах по всему миру. Он продолжает работать как продюсер и композитор с музыкантами из Канады, Южной Америки и Азии.

Выдающийся турецкий пианист XXI века Фазиль Сай продолжает параллельно сочинять музыку и играть на фортепиано. Фазиль Сай выступил на грандиозном Федеральном президентском концерте в Германии в 2019 году, исполнив произведения известных композиторов и несколько произведений, написанных им для этого концерта. Концерт, на котором присутствовал президент Германии Франк-Вальтер Штайнмайер и его жена, вызвал резонанс во всем мире.

Сочетая страстное музыкальное чувство, высокую виртуозность и интеллектуальный диапазон, исландский пианист Викингур Олафссон завоевал все награды в своей стране: четыре награды «Музыкант года» на церемонии вручения наград исландской музыки, а также премию «Исландский оптимизм».

Азербайджанская пианистка Хумай Гасымзаде окончила Нью-Йоркскую Манхэттенскую музыкальную школу. Свою талантливость пианистка подтвердила, выступив в цикле концертных программ «Музыкальный мост», организованных Азербайджано-американским музыкальным фондом. Среди пианистов, живших и творивших в Азербайджане XXI века, следует особо выделить имя Мурада Гусейнова. Его заслуги в развитии фортепианной школы в нашей стране неоспоримы.

Keywords: world pianists, interpretation, piano, Russia, China, Canada, modern era, XXI century, Azerbaijan piano school, Lang Lang, concert programs, jazz improvisations.

Ключевые слова: пианисты мира, интерпретация, фортепиано, Россия, Китай, Канада, современность, XXI век, Азербайджанская фортепианная школа, Ланг Ланг, концертные программы, джазовые импровизации.

The evolutionary process and the principles of gradual development in 21st century piano music are closely related. The modern achievements of the piano performance school are the result of the high level of piano pedagogy. The Russian piano school, which occupies an important place in world pianism, has produced a number of outstanding pianists. Among them: Denis Matsuyev, Yevgeny Kissin, Grigory Sokolov, Nikolai Lugansky and others should be mentioned.

The Russian school of performance had a great influence on the development of world piano music, and acquired its characteristic features from the second half of the 19th century and earlier. In the 21st century, representatives of the Russian piano school preserve their performance traditions and show new interpretations.

Denis Matsuyev, a talented pianist who has become famous all over the world in modern times, performs as a soloist of the Moscow State Philharmonic after graduating from the Moscow Conservatory. "Yeni adlar" is invited to concert-tours in foreign countries as a laureate of the competition held by the international public charity fund.

Continuing his piano career successfully, Denis gained world fame as the winner of the P. Tchaikovsky International Competition in 1998. As an innovator in piano performance, he enriches the Russian school of performance by applying new methods. Since 2004, in cooperation with local orchestras and leading collectives of foreign countries, he has been giving a series of concerts called "Soloist Denis Matsuyev". Performing with the Mariinsky Theater Orchestra conducted by

Valery Georgiev, the Russian National Orchestra conducted by Mikhail Pletnev, and the Orchestra of Soloists conducted by Vladimir Spivakov, he demonstrates his unique interpretation. Denis Matsuyev is famous as the only pianist who performed three piano concertos of P. Tchaikovsky in one evening. Music lovers admire his technical capabilities and virtuosity.

Denis Matsuyev has great love for the jazz genre and often completes his concerts with jazz miniatures and improvisations. In 2017, he surprised all his fans by presenting to the audience a new program "Jazz Among Friends" consisting of the musician's own works.

Denis Matsuyev regularly cooperates with New York Philharmonic, Chicago, Pittsburgh Symphony Orchestras, German Berlin Philharmonic, Bavarian Radio Orchestra, French National and Paris Orchestras, Great Britain's BBC Orchestra, London Orchestra. He demonstrates his unique interpretations in performances with world-renowned conductors such as Maris Jansons, Zubin Mehta, Kurt Masur, Paavo Järvi, Antonio Pappano, Charles Dutoit.

Among the achievements of the virtuoso pianist, the CD "Unknown Rachmaninov" dedicated to the genius composer Rachmaninov has a special place. In addition to his pianistic activities, the musician strives to make greater contributions to his people by leading numerous charity programs, promoting classical music among the youth, supporting young talents and organizing piano competitions.

In 2011, Denis Matsuyev was awarded the title of honorary professor of Moscow State University and became the organizer of the annual "Stars in Baikal" festival held in Irkutsk. Later, he acts as a member of the jury of the "Blue Bird" talent show of the Russia-1 channel.

On April 8, 2019, Denis Matsuyev performed a grand concert program at the Heydar Aliyev Palace in Azerbaijan. First Lady Mehriban Aliyeva, her daughters Leyla Aliyeva and Arzu Aliyeva, who participated in the concert program, welcomed the pianist's interpretation with applause.

In this concert, Denis Matsuyev performed L. Beethoven's "Sonata No. 17" for piano, S. Rahmanov's variations on Corelli for piano, "Ballad No. 4" by F. Chopin, "Thought" by P. Tchaikovsky, S. Prokofiev interprets "Sonata No. 7" for piano at a high level. Pianist presents works by George Gershwin, Duke Ellington, jazz standards in a new arrangement, interesting improvisations and rhythms. [И. Нилюлаев 2021, p.2]

Yevgeny Igorevich Kissin is one of the famous representatives of the Russian piano school. We must say with amazement that Kissin started improvising on the piano at the age of two, and at the age of six entered the Moscow Music College. At the age of ten, he interpreted Mozart's piano concerto with the Ulyanovsk State Symphony Orchestra, and a year later his solo concert was organized in Moscow [И. Нилюлаев 2021, p.3]

Yevgeny Kissin began to show his talent abroad and was awarded two Grammy awards: the first for the best solo performance of works by composers Scriabin and Stravinsky; and the second was received for the

performance of Prokofiev's concerto for piano and orchestra.

In 2001, Kissin was awarded an honorary doctorate by the Manhattan School of Music, in June 2005 by the London Royal Academy of Music, in 2009 by the University of Hong Kong, and in 2010 by the Jerusalem Hebrew University [wikipedia.Кисин_Евгений_Игоревич].

When interpreting Kissin's musical works, it is as if he is trying to recreate the work. Music critics rave about his unique interpretations.

The famous Russian pianist Nikolai Lugansky studied at the Moscow Central Music School and the Moscow Conservatory. The concert activity of the pianist started during his school years. He performs in the capital of Russia and other cities.

In 1988, Nikolai Lugansky took part in the Cannes International Festival and gained achievements [wikipedia.Луганский,_Николай_Львович].

After his first solo performance in France in 1990, Nikolay Lugansky began to give concerts all over the world. Thus, he performs in concert halls in Moscow, St. Petersburg, Amsterdam, Brussels, London, Paris, Milan, Munich, Los Angeles, New York, Madrid, Vienna, Tokyo and wins the sympathy of the audience with his interpretations. The pianist collaborates with the world's leading orchestras and more than 170 famous conductors. [belcanto.ru/lugansky.html]

Nikolay Lugansky Roc d'Anteron, Colmar, Montpellier and Nantes (France), Ruhr and Schleswig-Holstein (Germany), Verbier and I. Menuhin (Switzerland), Mozart Festival in England, "December Evenings", "Russian Winter" festivals in Moscow and is a regular participant of the world's most prestigious music festivals.

Nikolay Lugansky's discography includes recordings released by Melodiya, Erato Disques, Warner Classics, Deutsche Grammophon and other companies.

Although a generation of pianists such as Chen Sa, Li Yun-di, Shen Wenyu, Wang Yuichzia, and Zhang Haochen have been active in China in the 21st century, their performance art could not surpass the phenomenal achievements of Lang Lang. About this, Ge Shiyuy writes: "*Lang Lang became famous and became a star in the blink of an eye, surpassing everyone else.*" [Гэ Шиюй 2022, p. 143].

Lang Lang was born in Shenyang in 1982 into a family of pianists and studied music from a very early age. At the age of five, he won a competition of young pianists in his hometown of Shenyang, and at the age of nine he was admitted to the Beijing Central Conservatory of Music. 4 years later, Lang Lang won the First International Youth Competition held in Japan and gave a concert with the National Symphony Orchestra of China. Lang Lang continued his musical education at the Curtis Institute in Philadelphia. The Wall Street Journal called the pianist one of the "20 most famous young people in the world" [Гэ Шиюй 2022, p.147].

In 2009, Time magazine included Lang Lang among the 100 most influential performers of the year, calling the pianist "*a symbol of China's youth and its future. China owes its success in piano art to Lang Lang*" [Гэ Шиюй 2022, p.148].

A distinctive feature of Lang Lang's playing style was his facial expressions and free movements behind the instrument. Until the 21st century, such free movements behind the instrument have not been seen in the interpretations of any professional pianist.

For the first time in Steinway's history, one of the new piano models specially designed for teaching is named "The Lang Lang Piano" after a pianist.

Lang Lang collaborates with world-famous musicians: conductors Daniel Barenboim, Sir Simon Rattle, dubstep artist Marquis Scott and legendary jazz representative Herbie Hancock.

The pianist is working hard to establish cultural links between East and West and introduce Chinese listeners to Western music.

In 2004, the pianist was selected as a UNICEF Goodwill Ambassador, and four years later he was China's cultural ambassador to the United States and founded the International Fund to attract new talents to music.

Along with China, the role of South Korean musicians in the development of the world school of pianism is undeniable. Among them, pianist Son-Jin Cho learned to play the piano at the age of six and gave his first concert at the age of eleven.

In 2008, the young musician won the International Chopin Piano Competition, and in 2009, the International Piano Competition held in Hamamatsu (Japan). In 2011, he was awarded the 3rd place in the PTchaikovsky Competition in Moscow and the 3rd place in the Arthur Rubinstein International Piano Competition in Tel Aviv in 2014. The pianist constantly works on himself, interprets and records new works. Son-Jin Cho was not satisfied with his success and always strived to move forward. As a result of these efforts, the pianist became the first Korean pianist to win the 1st prize and gold medal at the Chopin International Piano Competition held in Warsaw in 2015 [wikipedia. Чо Сон Чжин].

In 2016, he performed in Vladivostok with the Symphony Orchestra of the Mariinsky Theater conducted by Valery Georgiev, professionally interpreting S. Rachmaninov's "Symphonic Dances" and the third piano concerto.

The musician collaborates with such prominent conductors as the Munich Philharmonic Orchestra, the Czech Philharmonic Orchestra, the Royal Concertgebouw Orchestra (Amsterdam), the NHK Symphony Orchestra (Tokyo), Chon Myung-hun, Lorin Maazel, Mikhail Pletnev. He has performed high-class, audience-enthraling performances at New York's Carnegie Hall, Berlin Philharmonic, Vienna Concert Hall, Munich's Prince-Regent Theater, Stuttgart's Liederhalle, Tokyo's Suntory Hall, the Walt Disney Concert Hall in Los Angeles, and many other venues. [Lee Hyo-won 2019, p.9]

Contemporary Canadian pianist Jan Lisetsky studied piano at the Mount Royal Conservatory in Calgary at the age of five and has been performing as a soloist in orchestras. At the age of 14, the young pianist took part in international competitions and amazed the audience with his interpretations on the 200th anniversary of Friedrich Chopin. Replacing the ill Nelson Freire on

a tour of France, he made his name among the world's pianists. He is distinguished by his high-level interpretations at the opening concert of the international music festival in Seoul, and at the concert in Ottawa on the occasion of the visit of Queen Elizabeth II to Canada. [wikipedia. Lisetsky,_Jan]

Jan Lisetsky's performances have been widely broadcast by leading radio and television networks in Europe and North America, and he was featured in the CBC National News documentary *The Prodigy*. In 2013, he received the Leonard Bernstein Award at the Schleswig-Holstein Music Festival and was named Young Pianist of the Year by Gramophone magazine. The pianist signed an exclusive contract with the Deutsche Grammophon record company and recorded several discs. He interprets W.Mozart's 20th and 21st concerts with the Bavarian Radio Symphony Orchestra in a unique and unique way. These interpretations also impress the critics and they confirm that Jan Lisetski is a genius pianist. [Arthur Kaptainis., p.2].

On the side, Yan is involved in philanthropy and has performed with organizations such as the David Foster Foundation, the Polish Humanitarian Organization, and the Star Wish Foundation. Since 2008, he has been appointed the National Youth Ambassador, and in 2012, the UNICEF Ambassador to Canada. [Zachary Woolfe. p. 10]

Canadian pianist and composer Steve Barakatt has been playing the piano since he was 4 years old, and has been engaged in arranging since he was very young. At the age of 14, he recorded his first solo album, *Double Happiness*, which quickly became a top 20 best-selling album in Canada. In the following years, the pianist recorded a number of albums at Poly-Gram, Universal and Victor Entertainment studios and released the albums "Audace", "Escape", "Steve Barakatt LIVE", "Quebec", "Eternity", "A Love Affair and All About Us". does. [wikipedia. Steve_Barakatt]

In 2007, Steve Barakatt recorded his first vocal album: *Here I Am*, accompanied by the London Foundation Philharmonic Orchestra at George Martin's AIR Studios in London. This album resonates all over the world. Steve has performed as a pianist for over 500 events regionally, nationally and internationally on many stages around the world. He continues to work as a producer and composer with musicians from Canada, South America and Asia.

In cooperation with famous artists in Hong Kong, he composes the song "Mou Tian" performed by four Asian stars.

In 2024, the famous musician Steve Barakatt won the sympathy of our people by performing as a composer and pianist at the Heydar Aliyev Center in Baku. [cebheinfo.az/medeniyyet]. The event takes place within the framework of the world tour of the pianist-composer "Neorallig". The concert consists of two parts, the most popular works of the composer are included in the program. Pianist-composer Steve Barakatt expertly interprets classical works and jazz interpretations. The musician is the author of "Laylay", the anthem of UNICEF, many of his works are played on more than 150 TV shows around the world, including the Monaco Grand Prix.

Fazil Say, the outstanding Turkish pianist of the 21st century, takes piano lessons from David Levin at the Robert Schuman College of Music in Düsseldorf. Composer Aribert Reyman heard Fazil Say's performance on a concert-tour trip to Ankara and praised him and said to outstanding pianist David Levine: "*Fazil Say has a great future as a pianist.*" [Paganini Variations, 1995].

In 1991-1995, the pianist continued his studies in Berlin, mastering the secrets of composition and piano playing more deeply. His playing technique allowed him to master the repertoire very quickly and incredibly. [Schwarze Hymnen for violin and piano, 1987, p.22]

Fazil Say continues composing and playing piano in parallel. As a pianist, his repertoire includes works by classical composers as well as works by contemporary composers. He interprets I. Stravinsky's "Holy Spring" for two pianos with great enthusiasm, working for his solo performance. Fazil Say's concerts as a pianist in France are highly appreciated by music lovers, and the French newspaper "Le Figaro" calls him a genius and writes: "*Fazil Say's performances with symphonic and chamber orchestras can be considered as a victory of modern pianistic art.*" [Jean-Pierre Thiollet. 2015, p. 193]

From 2005 to 2011, he was distinguished by his high-level interpretation at the Dortmund concert hall, the Berlin Konzerthaus residency and the Schleswig-Holstein festival. His performance at the Hessischer Rundfunk residency in Frankfurt am Main was a triumph for the Turkish world. Fazil Say's concert tours in Russia are very successful, and here he becomes famous as a pianist-composer and signs a contract with the Russian punk rock band NAIV (Новые Арлекины и Вольтижеры).

Fazil Say performed at the grand Federal Presidential Concert in Germany in 2019, performing the works of well-known composers and several pieces he composed for this concert. At the concert, conductor Stephen Sloane and the accompaniment of the Bremen Philharmonic Orchestra received special applause from the audience. The concert, attended by the President of Germany Frank-Walter Steinmeier and his wife, reverberates around the world.

In May 2022, Fazil Say, having received an invitation for a concert tour to our country, is pleased to perform high-level performances in the Heydar Aliyev Palace. The world-famous pianist cooperates with the Azerbaijani cellist Jamal Aliyev and together with him gives a series of concert programs in America and Canada. Both performers show virtuosity at concerts held in Los Angeles, New York, Chicago, Washington, Toronto and Boston. [baku.ws/mdniyyt/166220]

The outstanding Icelandic pianist and composer Vikingur Ólafsson is renowned for his performances with the world's leading orchestras as a multi-award winner. The New York Times called Ólafsson the Glenn Gould of Iceland after his virtuoso performance of Philip Glass's Piano works. Vikingur performed successfully as a soloist at the opening of the new Harpa Concert Hall in Reykjavík, accompanied by the Ice-

landic Symphony Orchestra under the direction of conductor Vladimir Ashkenazi. [ru.fw.wiki.Vikingur_Ólafsson]

With a combination of passionate musical feeling, high virtuosity and intellectual range, Icelandic pianist Vikingur Ólafsson has won all the honors in his country: four Musician of the Year awards at the Icelandic Music Awards, as well as the Icelandic Optimism Award.

"*The New York Times*" newspaper praised the pianist's "*volcanic interpretations, ideal virtuosity, ease and taste for complex compositions.*" [Smith C., 2016, p.7]

Ólafsson receives invitations to the world's most prestigious concert halls and festivals, and also becomes their resident musician. The most famous modern composers trust him to perform the premieres of new works.

Under the direction of pianist John Adams, he performs with the Bergen Philharmonic Orchestra (conductor Edward Gardner), Cleveland Orchestra and Orchestra of the National Academy of Santa Cecilia, New York Philharmonic Orchestra (conductor Semyon Bychkov), Camerata Salzburg Orchestra. Conducted by Andrew Manze, he also collaborates with the Los Angeles Philharmonic (conductor Gustavo Dudamel), expertly interpreting works by classical and contemporary composers.

The 21st century Republic of Azerbaijan has a mature piano school, characterized by progressive traditions, and has trained a generation of talented pianists. Azerbaijan's piano performance, which has actively adopted the experience of Russian and Western European performance, is inseparably connected with national traditions. Prominent Azerbaijani musicologist Tarlan Seyidov writes about this: "*Azerbaijani piano music is in close contact with European piano art. The experts invited to the development of the art of piano in Azerbaijan and the training of national personnel: N.D.Nikolayev, M.L.Presman, I.S.Aysberg made a worthy contribution*" [T. Seyidov, 2016, p. 42-43].

Today, the Azerbaijan-American Music Foundation (AAMF) supports the development of cultural relations between these two countries. AAMF organized a series of concert programs called "Musical Bridge" with the participation of prominent musicians. [19]. In this program, pianist Humay Gasimzade represented our country at a high level. At the "Music Bridge" concerts, along with the works of American composers, Humay Gasimzade surprised the audience by professionally interpreting the "Waltz" from the ballet "Lightning Roads" by Gara Garayev and the play for piano by Khayyam Mirzazade. American William Hayter, associate professor of the music department at Midwestern University in Wichita Falls, Texas, expressed his opinion as follows: "*Azerbaijani people are a happy nation that has genius composers and talented pianists like Gara Garayev and Khayyam Mirzazade.*" [A. Aliyeva, 2023 p. 7].

In his interpretation, Humay Gasimzade reconciled Eastern and Western music at a high level. A number of works accepted at the international level were the object of research in the doctoral dissertation defended

by Humay Gasimzadeh at Boling Green University in the United States, and by the decision of the university's scientific council, that dissertation was awarded the prize for the best scientific work of the year.

Among the pianists who lived and worked in Azerbaijan in the 21st century, we should especially emphasize the name of Murad Huseynov. His services in the development of the piano school in our country are undeniable.

The pianist is a laureate of the international piano competitions held in Tbilisi in 1997 and in France in 1998, and the winner of the 3rd Francis Poulenc international piano competition held in Limoges in 2002. Murad Huseynov won three special awards for his high-level interpretation of the works of French composers [M. Huseynov, 2020].

The pianist represents Azerbaijan's piano performance at a high level at the Bach Music Festival in Istanbul, the Hiroshima Piano Festival, the Musical Kremlin Festival in Moscow and in various countries around the world. He performed unique interpretations with the London Royal Philharmonic Orchestra, Limoges Symphony Orchestra, Azerbaijan State Symphony Orchestra, Gara Garayev State Chamber Orchestra, New Russian Quartet. Musician's P.I. Performances in the Rachmaninov hall of the Moscow State Conservatory named after Tchaikovsky, the main hall of the French Senate, the State Kremlin Palace, the International Diplomatic Academy, Pleyel, Corto halls, Jamal Rashid Ray, Danube Palace can be considered an achievement of Azerbaijani musical culture [Conway, P.; Swierczewski, J., 2017, p.4].

Thus, when examining the stylistic features of world pianism, it became clear that the world school of piano playing has been an integral part of musical culture and has passed a great progressive path. In the 21st century, piano playing has become more developed all over the world. In our modern times, talented pianists are active in several countries of the world. The successful formation of Azerbaijani piano culture is organically connected with the best traditions and new achievements of Russian and European piano music. Thanks to the interaction of these factors, the modern piano performance of Azerbaijan has reached a high professional level.

Literature:

1. Arthur Kaptainis. Canadian Jan Lisiecki on edge of greatness Архивная копия от 3 марта 2013 на Wayback Machine // The Montreal Gazette, January 11, 2013.

2. Гэ Шиюй. Lang Lang: New Trends in Academic Musical Art. Journal of Musical Science. 2022. T. 10, No. 3, pp. 142-150.

3. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Кисин_Евгений_Игоревич

4. Nilolaev I. Biography of Evgenia Kisin. RIA Novosti. October 10, 2021, No. 10

5. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Луганский,_Николай_Львович

6. <https://www.belcanto.ru/lugansky.html>

7. Lee Hуо-won. 15-Year-Old Becomes 1st Asian Winner of Hamamatsu Contest Архивная копия от 18 сентября 2019 на Wayback Machine // The Korea Times, 23.11.2009.

8. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Чо_Сон_Чжин

9. https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Лисецкий,_Ян

10. Zachary Woolfe. A Young Star, Team Player Архивная копия от 16 декабря 2012 на Wayback Machine // The New York Times, December 14, 2012.

11. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Steve_Barakatt

12. <https://ce-bheinfo.az/medeniyyet/dunyasohretli-stiv-barakattin-bakida-konserti-olacag>

13. Paganini Variations (for Piano), Yapı Kredi Publications, Istanbul, 1995.

14. Schwarze Hymnen for violin and piano, Verlag für Musik-Enzyklopaedie, 1987.

15. Jean-Pierre Thiollet. Neva editions, 2015, p. 193. (ISBN 978-2-3505-5192-0)

16. <https://baku.ws/mdniyyt/166220>

17. https://ru.frwiki.wiki/wiki/Vikingur_Ólafsson

18. Smith C., "In Iceland, the festival of the present and future", The New York Times, The New York Times (as of November 15, 2016)

19. <https://medeniyyet.az/page/news/51408/Musiqi-korpusu-senet-irsimizi-Amerikada-teblig-edir.html>

20. Aliyeva A. "Cadenza" orchestra added color to the holidays. Culture and Art newspaper. Baku, 05.01.2023.

21. Seyidov T. Azerbaijani piano culture of the 20th century. Baku, Education, 2016, 336 pages.

22. Huseynov M. (PDF). caspianetude.az (English). International Competition for Young Pianists. Date of use: February 9, 2020.

23. Conway, P.; Swierczewski, J. Gara Garayev Sonata for Violin and Piano; 24 Preludes for Piano (PDF) (English). London: Toccata Classics. 2017. p. 12. Archived from the original on 2021-09-01 (PDF).